

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 3

First call for projects in Service 1 Milestone M4.1

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.1

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
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ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.1

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Type:

Dissemination level:

Delivery date:

M4

Means of verifications:

Call for project released on the website.

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

Comments:

The call for proposals for ESiWACE3 Service 1 has been uploaded to the ESiWACE website on April 27, 2023. It is publicly accessible under the following URL:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support>

Call for proposals

We offer to collaborate with developers of weather and climate models to improve model efficiency and readying the software to enable model execution on existing and near-future hardware architectures.

Call For Proposals 2023-2024

Home / Services / Software Support

The "Call for Proposals for Collaborations to prepare Europe's Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale Systems" is now open.

The ESIWACE3 Consortium has just published a "Call for proposals" to apply for some of the services provided by the third phase of ESIWACE - Center of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe. This call aims to support the exascale preparations for the European ESM community.

The call is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM codes, not only the ESIWACE3 partners. It will run from 1 May 2023 at 14:00 h CEST until 1 November 2023 at 14:00 h CET.

With this service, the ESIWACE3 Consortium expect to establish collaborative projects in which the ESIWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant. Apart from offering limited engineering time and implementing code modifications, the projects aim to provide guidance and establish knowledge transfer between HPC experts and modelling groups.

The description and more details of the call can be found [here \(PDF\)](#).

Please prepare the application following the instruction included in the call and then [submit it using our online form](#).